

Variable stiffness control for assistive walkers

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Abstract—We propose a robotic solution for guiding older adults with mild cognitive deficits using a passive robotic walker called FriWalk. Our key contribution is a guidance mechanism that ensures user freedom while following a path. It stiffens when the user drifts off the path and switches to a "vehicle compliance mode" when the user aligns with the path. The paper includes theoretical proofs of the mechanism's correctness, and simulations and experiments demonstrate a strong balance between user safety and comfort.

Index Terms—Physical Human-Robot Interaction, Physically Assistive Devices, Rehabilitation Robotics

Fig. 1. (a) The *FriWalk* robotic walker used in our experiments. (b) Adopted reference frames.

I. INTRODUCTION

This extended abstract discusses the design of a control scheme for an assistive robot called the Friendly Walker (*FriWalk*) that provides guidance and assistance to older adults. We propose a hybrid control scheme that incorporates variable stiffness control, allowing the user and the system to share control of the robot. We also highlight the importance of physical interaction between the robot and the user. The concept of shared control is implemented at the level of the motion control algorithm, and a variable steering mechanism is implemented using the torque controller to reduce hardware complexity.

Robotic walkers have emerged as a promising solution for assisting older adults [1]. Passive robot paradigms [2], where the user is responsible for locomotion, have influenced the design of these devices. The physical interaction between the system and the user is crucial [3], as safety and user comfort are important considerations. Different sensor and actuator configurations have been explored, such as electromagnetic brakes and motor-actuated back wheels [4], [5]. Actuation on the back wheels disrupts system passivity, but it allows for a larger set of comfortable maneuvers. Shared control mechanisms have been proposed to mediate between user intent and system control [6]. In this work, we focus on the motion control algorithm to achieve a smooth transition between user and system control. The interaction forces with the ground are reflected in the motor currents, enabling a variable steering mechanism without direct force measurement.

A. Problem Formulation

The robotic walker in Figure 1-a assists the user in navigating complex environments. Equipped with sensors for localization and obstacle detection, it allows the user to control forward velocity while using two actuated steering wheels. By using the single track model, the two steering wheels can be modelled as a single virtual wheel. This results in a front-steering bicycle model [7].

The virtual steering angle φ is related to the left and right wheel angles φ_l and φ_r via the Ackerman steering condition, ensuring the proper positioning of the vehicle's instantaneous rotation center (ICR) (see Figure 1-b).

We define the ground reference frame $\{O_w, X_w, Y_w, Z_w\}$ the world fixed reference frame at ground level. The path following problem is formulated in a Frenet reference frame, denoted as $\{O_f, X_f, Y_f, Z_f\}$ (Figure 1-b). Let θ_d be the angle between X_f and X_w , and $\theta = \theta - \theta_d$, where θ is the vehicle yaw. The vehicle reference point O_m has coordinates $[l_x, l_y]$ in the Frenet frame, while the origin of the Frenet frame O_f has curvilinear abscissa s along the path. The velocity \dot{s} of the Frenet frame along the path can be considered as an additional control input. We define d as the distance between O_m and the contact point of the virtual front wheel.

Using the new set of coordinates $[l_x, l_y, \tilde{\theta}]^T$, the vehicle model can be reformulated as [8]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{l}_x &= -\dot{s}(1 - c(s)l_y) + v \cos \tilde{\theta}, \\ \dot{l}_y &= -c(s)\dot{s}l_x + v \sin \tilde{\theta}, \\ \dot{\tilde{\theta}} &= \omega - c(s)\dot{s}, \\ \dot{\varphi} &= u_v, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $c(s) = \frac{d\theta_d}{ds}(s)$ is the path curvature, and $\omega = \frac{v}{d} \tan(\varphi)$ is the vehicle angular velocity. In this new formulation, the state vector of the vehicle is given by $\chi = [l_x, l_y, \tilde{\theta}, \varphi]^T$, as in (1), or $\bar{\chi} = [x, y, \theta, \varphi]^T$, if we consider the differential kinematics of the front-steering rear-driven bicycle in the world reference frame. Since the vehicle is passive, the forward velocity v is an exogenous control input imposed by the assisted person (AP), while the steering velocity u_v is a control input.

The path following objectives can be now defined as:

$$\begin{cases} \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} |l_x(t)| \leq l_\infty, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} |l_y(t)| \leq l_\infty, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} |\tilde{\theta}(t)| \leq \tilde{\theta}_\infty, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where t denotes the time, and $l_\infty > 0$ and $\tilde{\theta}_\infty > 0$ are positive arbitrary constants.

The control authority is shared between the robot and the user using a variable stiffness vehicle handling strategy. The motor control is based on a permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) and can operate in torque-tracking or velocity-tracking mode. The torque-tracking mode tracks a desired torque, while the velocity-tracking mode tracks a desired velocity.

II. SOLUTION OVERVIEW

A. Approach Description

The controller implementing the variable stiffness approach has two working modes: stiff velocity tracking and compliant torque tracking. In the stiff velocity tracking mode, the controller uses full authority to reduce path errors. In the compliant torque tracking mode, the control authority is gradually released to the user. The stiff mode is used to override the user's command in dangerous situations, while the compliant mode is used to vary the vehicle's stiffness. The working modes are labelled with a logic variable $q \in \{0, 1\}$: $q = 1$ indicates that the velocity-tracking mode is enabled, while $q = 0$ indicates that the torque-tracking mode is enabled. The controller design involves a feedback control law regulating the velocity for full control authority, a feedback control law regulating the torque and a measure of distance from the path for variable stiffness control, and a switching law between the two modes. The reference velocity (control input) is independent of the motor's working mode. The control synthesis for the velocity-tracking mode is based on a backstepping approach, where the steering velocity is designed to ensure the convergence of the steering angle to a desired value. The desired value is used to define the equilibrium

position of the variable stiffness system in the torque-tracking mode.

To avoid the singularity of zero velocity, the steering command is designed to avoid $\varphi \approx \pm 90^\circ$ when the vehicle stops.

$$\varphi^*(\chi, v) = \arctan\left(\frac{d}{v}\omega(\chi, v)\right). \quad (3)$$

An approaching angle strategy is used to stabilize the dynamics of the path following controller. The path is properly approached and followed if the approaching angle is continuous, strictly monotonic and odd, and satisfies certain conditions.

$$\delta(l_y) = -\frac{\pi}{2} \tanh\left(\frac{l_y}{2}\right). \quad (4)$$

The distance from the path is measured using the difference between the orientation error and the approaching angle.

$$|e_\theta| = |\tilde{\theta} - \delta(l_y)| < |\delta(l_y)|. \quad (5)$$

B. Variable Stiffness Controller

The variable stiffness controller is based on two controllers: a stiff path following controller and a vehicle compliance controller. The stiff path following controller is active when the distance from the target orientation is large, and the vehicle compliance controller becomes active when the distance is small.

The stiff path following controller is designed using the motor in the velocity-tracking mode, and it ensures convergence of the vehicle attitude towards the desired approaching angle.

Assumption 1 (Persistent motion): The forward velocity $v \geq 0$ of the vehicle satisfies

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v(t) \neq 0.$$

This assumption simply states that whenever the user stops his/her motion, he/she restarts in finite time.

Theorem 2 (Stiff path following): Consider the vehicle kinematic model (1), Assumption 1, and an approaching angle $\delta(l_y)$ continuous, strictly monotonic and odd satisfying $l_y \delta(l_y) \leq 0$ and $|\delta(l_y)| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\forall l_y$. Then the passive path following problem (2) is solved with $l_\infty = \tilde{\theta}_\infty = 0$ by the control actions

$$\begin{aligned} u_v &= \dot{\varphi}^* - \kappa_\varphi \sin\left(\frac{e_\varphi}{2}\right) + \\ &\quad - v \eta \max\left(0, \text{sign}\left(\frac{\eta}{2} \sin\left(\frac{e_\varphi}{2}\right) - \frac{\kappa_\theta}{m} e_\theta^2\right)\right), \\ \dot{s} &= v \dot{\xi}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\xi} &= \cos \tilde{\theta} + \kappa_x l_x, \\
\ddot{\xi} &= -\sin \tilde{\theta} \left(\frac{v}{d} \tan \varphi - c(s)v \dot{\xi} \right) + \\
&\quad - \kappa_x v \dot{\xi} (1 - c(s)l_y) + \kappa_x v \cos \tilde{\theta}, \\
\gamma &= \dot{\xi} c(s) + \frac{d\delta}{dl_y}(l_y) \left(-c(s)\dot{\xi} l_x + \sin \tilde{\theta} \right), \\
\varphi^* &= \arctan(d(\gamma - \kappa_\theta e_\theta)), \\
\dot{\varphi}^* &= \frac{d}{1 + (d(\gamma - \kappa_\theta e_\theta))^2} \left\{ c(s)\ddot{\xi} + \frac{dc}{ds}(s)v\dot{\xi}^2 + \right. \\
&\quad + \frac{d^2\delta}{dl_y^2}(l_y)v \left(-c(s)\dot{\xi} l_x + \sin \tilde{\theta} \right)^2 + \\
&\quad - \frac{d\delta}{dl_y}(l_y)(\ddot{\xi} c(s)l_x + \dot{\xi} \left[\frac{dc}{ds}(s)v\dot{\xi} l_x + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + c(s)\dot{l}_x \right] - \dot{\tilde{\theta}} \cos \tilde{\theta} \right) + \\
&\quad \left. - \kappa_\theta \left(\dot{\tilde{\theta}} - \frac{d\delta}{dl_y}(l_y)\dot{l}_y \right) \right\}, \\
e_\theta &= \tilde{\theta} - \delta(l_y), \\
e_\varphi &= \varphi - \varphi^*, \\
\eta &= \frac{4e_\theta \cos\left(\frac{e_\varphi}{2}\right)}{d \cos(\varphi^*) \cos(\varphi)},
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

and where $\kappa_\theta > 0$, $\kappa_\varphi > 0$, $\kappa_x > 0$, and $m > 1$ are constants.

The vehicle compliance controller modulates the stiffness of the system based on the vehicle's state, with a smaller stiffness when the vehicle is close to the path. The equilibrium position of the mass-spring damper is defined by the desired steering angle φ^* and the desired steering velocity $\dot{\varphi}^*$ computed by the stiff path following controller (7)

$$u_\tau = -\kappa_p (\varphi - \varphi^*) - \kappa_v (v_\varphi - \dot{\varphi}^*), \tag{8}$$

where the positive gains κ_p and κ_v vary on the basis of the distance between the vehicle and the path. The steering velocity $\dot{\varphi} = v_\varphi$. The gains are computed as cycloidal functions of the attitude error,

$$\begin{aligned}
\kappa_p(e_\theta, \Theta, \bar{\kappa}_p) &= \bar{\kappa}_p \left(\frac{|e_\theta|}{\Theta} - \frac{1}{2\pi} \sin \left(\frac{2\pi|e_\theta|}{\Theta} \right) \right), \\
\kappa_v(e_\theta, \Theta, \bar{\kappa}_v) &= \bar{\kappa}_v \left(\frac{|e_\theta|}{\Theta} - \frac{1}{2\pi} \sin \left(\frac{2\pi|e_\theta|}{\Theta} \right) \right),
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where the constants $\bar{\kappa}_p > 0$ and $\bar{\kappa}_v > 0$ are the maxima values for the gains κ_p and κ_v , and $\Theta \in [0, \frac{3}{2}\pi]$ is the tolerated attitude error threshold.

The two controllers are combined using a hybrid control law that switches between the velocity-tracking mode and the torque-tracking mode based on the value of a Lyapunov function.

$$V(\chi) = \frac{1}{2}e_\theta^2 + 1 - \cos\left(\frac{e_\varphi}{2}\right). \tag{10}$$

The hybrid control law ensures that the vehicle follows the path with limited errors. The hybrid model embeds the

Fig. 2. Experimental effects of singular velocities. The proposed algorithm (labeled “ φ_d ”) lets the vehicle remain in the path when the singularity happens, which is not the case for the compared controllers (labeled “ φ_1 ” and “ φ_2 ”).

dynamics of the steering velocity v_φ by introducing two states v_{φ_0} and t_j with discrete dynamics only, representing the initial condition of the integrator and the time instant in which the working mode is updated by the jump map, respectively. We have

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\varphi} &= qu_v + (1 - q) \cdot \\ &\quad \cdot \left(v_{\varphi_0} + \int_{t_j}^t \frac{u_\tau}{J_{eq}} dt \right), \\ \dot{v}_{\varphi_0} &= 0, \\ \dot{q} &= 0, \\ \dot{t}_j &= 0, \end{cases} \quad [\chi, v_{\varphi_0}, q, t_j]^T \in \mathcal{C}, \tag{11}$$

$$\begin{cases} \varphi^+ &= \varphi \\ v_{\varphi_0}^+ &= u_v, \\ q^+ &= 1 - q, \\ t_j^+ &= t, \end{cases} \quad [\chi, v_{\varphi_0}, q, t_j]^T \in \mathcal{D}, \tag{12}$$

where u_v and u_τ are computed as (6) and (8), respectively, and $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{C}_0 \cup \mathcal{C}_1$ and $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_0 \cup \mathcal{D}_1$ are the flow set and the jump set, respectively, defined via

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}_0 &= \{V(\chi) \leq V_{\text{out}} \wedge q = 0\}, \\
\mathcal{C}_1 &= \{V(\chi) \geq V_{\text{in}} \wedge q = 1\}, \\
\mathcal{D}_0 &= \{V(\chi) \geq V_{\text{out}} \wedge q = 0\}, \\
\mathcal{D}_1 &= \{V(\chi) \leq V_{\text{in}} \wedge q = 1\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

$V(\chi) \geq 0$ is the Lyapunov function (Eq. 10), designed to trigger the switching of the motor mode q , and $V_{\text{out}} > V_{\text{in}} > 0$ are positive constants. The condition $V_{\text{out}} > V_{\text{in}}$ ensures that the jumps of q takes place with hysteresis.

III. RESULTS

A. Experiments

The proposed approach was tested in a number of experiments conducted at the University of Trento. The results obtained are described next.

B. Harnessing steering singularities

In the first set of experiments, the system's ability to handle the steering singularity was tested. The singularity occurs

Fig. 3. Paths followed with cooperative users.

Fig. 4. Paths followed with uncooperative users.

when the velocity is zero. The effects of the singularity on user comfort and control accuracy were evaluated. Users were asked to push the vehicle forward on a straight path, stop at a marked position, and then continue along the path. The vehicle compliance was disabled to expose the effect of the singularity. The trajectories observed in the experiments are shown in Figure 2. Three different control laws for the virtual steering angle were used: φ_d , φ_1 , and φ_2 . The proposed controller φ_d was found to be insensitive to the singularity, while the other two controllers experienced problems after the stop.

C. Experimental comparison

The authority-sharing control law was tested with cooperative and non-cooperative users. Non-cooperative users were instructed to push the vehicle away from the path, while cooperative users were asked to follow the path with the help of a tablet. The paths followed by cooperative and non-cooperative users are shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. The cooperation index (Eq. 14), which quantifies the level of cooperation between the user and the robot, was computed for each test.

$$I_c = \left(\frac{1}{L_{\text{path}}} \int_0^{s_{\text{final}}} (i_r^2 + i_l^2) d\bar{s} \right)^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

The cooperation indices for the cooperative tests were significantly higher than those for the non-cooperative tests, indicating better user-robot collaboration.

D. Quantitative analysis

A quantitative study was performed with 20 users. Each user was asked to follow a path using the variable stiffness controller. The paths followed by the users are shown in

Fig. 5. Examples of followed paths by users guided with variable stiffness handling.

Figure 5. The mean cooperation index for all the experiments was 3.07 A^{-2} , indicating a good level of cooperation between the users and the robot.

IV. CONCLUSION

The authors present a new authority-sharing technology for robotic walkers that utilises a control strategy to adjust the stiffness and compliance of the system based on the path tracking error. The system operates in two modes: stiff path following mode and vehicle compliance mode. The application of hybrid control theory ensures theoretical guarantees on tracking error bounds. Simulations and experimental data demonstrate that the system minimizes the use of the stiff velocity tracking mode and guides the user gently towards the desired path. The authors propose a cooperation index to quantify the quality of user-robot interaction and suggest future research directions, including adjusting vehicle compliance based on environmental conditions and investigating the correlation between the cooperation index and the user's mental state.

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